

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF MUSIC ART IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: The article discusses the role of music in human life, its educational significance, and its role in the system of aesthetic education. Based on the opinions of famous scientists, it is shown that music is an integral part of the aesthetic education of young people in the family, preschool educational organizations, as well as in the school system. Taking into account that music is a powerful educational tool, it is emphasized that it is necessary to pay more serious attention to music lessons in preschool educational organizations.

Key words: national musical art, education, upbringing, outlook, ability, talent, imagination, behavior, emotion, musical language, form.

Introduction:

As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, "*Our national art of music, without a doubt, has a rich and ancient history.*"¹ Music is an art form that unites people through their experiences and emotional feelings. It becomes a means of communication between them. It can be called a miracle that the music created by one composer evokes different experiences in the hearts of other people.

Music education is a component of aesthetic education. Education is one of the leading factors that shape a person's personality. Aesthetic education, as its component, is based on the doctrine of the essence of beauty, the unity of aesthetic and moral feelings, the nationalism of art, expands and deepens people's knowledge of the objective world, develops their creative ability and talent. and helps to develop high spiritual qualities in them. It is usually understood that the goal of aesthetic education is to develop aesthetic feelings and thoughts in children, to be able to see and enjoy beauty.

In fact, the goals and tasks of aesthetic education are not limited to this, they teach students to understand and see beauty and ugliness, high and low, joy and sadness. Aesthetic education serves to establish universal and national values. It is clear that education affects a person's mind, feelings, imagination, beliefs, outlook, actions, and behavior.

The language of music is understandable and close to everyone. Music reflects thoughts and feelings through sounds, and describes the moral problems that have affected humanity in the stages of life. Philosophical essence of music is also revealed in this. Great musical works are imbued with deep philosophical content, music reflects issues such as life and death, individual and society, virtue and oppression, power and weakness. Musicologists, thinkers and scientists have been interested in musicologists, thinkers and scientists since ancient times. Philosophers, psychologists, pedagogues and public figures have tried to

¹ Mirziyoev Sh. The art of connecting hearts to hearts and hands to hands. // "Khalk sozi" newspaper, issue of September 8, 2018.

determine the features of music that influence the formation of a person as a person. Since ancient times, there have been ideas about the influence of music, especially its components - rhythm and melody, on human mood, changing his inner world. The art of music, as an important factor of aesthetic education, has a strong influence on personality formation.

Proper organization of music classes in the family, in pre-school educational organizations, at school is an effective way to enrich the inner world of the young generation and to understand art correctly. Music expresses human feelings, hopes, desires in its own artistic language and actively influences human emotions. Music is both science and art. It is based on physics and mathematics, which make music a science. But you can't look at a piece of music as a static concept of this science. Because music is a living art that is always developing.

The art of music becomes a companion of a person from the first years of his life and makes a significant contribution to the general cultural development. Music is a constant companion of human life. According to Stendhal, music is one of the forms of art that can penetrate deep into the heart of a person and reflect his inner experiences. *"Music belongs to the system of expressive art. Music also expresses events. But it is not determined by the dimensions of space and material objects, as in architecture. Music is perceived not by sight, but by hearing. Since the theme of music has its own characteristics and cannot cover all aspects of a person and reality, it primarily expresses the inner spiritual world of a person, his feelings and mood... music creates an emotional image of reality."*

Music has a wide range of mood expression. Human mood is a complex emotion that is not connected to anything. Mood has a generalized character, secondary aspects are excluded from it, and the most important aspects that determine the emotional attitude of a person to reality are distinguished. The power of music is that it can express happiness, sadness, imagination, endurance, courage, depression and similar human mental states in a private and general way, in their interdependence, in their absorption into each other. The "language" of music expresses the unity of all parts, the form of the work. Form is a material expression of musical content. The composer's thoughts, feelings, and imagination reach the listeners through the musical form. Therefore, it opens a wide way to master the "language" of music, to understand its essence, to master the wealth of thoughts, feelings, and experiences in music.

Ancient thinkers emphasized the importance of musical education for the growing generation. The human and positive qualities of a future member of society are formed right from childhood. It was during this period that music was considered a means of forming positive qualities. Music is created in the composition of singing and dancing, and later becomes an independent type of artistic creation, has a very specific "language" of artistic expression, specially designed and selected sounds are the source of this "language". Of course, music does not determine the directions of personality formation and its positive qualities by itself.

In recent years, considerable attention has been paid to musical education in pre-school education organizations. Internationally held "Sounds of Navruz" multi-voice folk instrument ensembles and orchestras festival is a clear proof of our opinion. At this festival, the fact that our little children take a musical instrument in their hands and try to play a tune makes people happy. Well, not all of them may become musicians and artists in the future, but the

fact that they are familiar with the art of music and know the alphabet of the art of music will be an incentive for them to have a good education in the future. It is undeniable.

The most important aspects of the educational effect depend on the ideological content of the musical work. Thus, the tasks of musical-aesthetic education are determined. The famous Polish composer K. Szymanowski in his article entitled "*Educational value of music in society*", talking about the natural power of music - that it can be used in two opposite directions - to create and destroy - directing it to the necessary work, "*It is necessary to use the power of music effectively, just like using the waters of a fast-flowing river for useful and productive work, i.e. to turn a mill.*" The effect of music on a person, its place in the spiritual life of an individual and society is a complex problem. This complexity and diversity did not come to science by itself. At this point, it is appropriate to recall Asafyev's words: "*...music is both art, science, language, and game.*" Therefore, the role of music in the formation of musical and personal characteristics of children is incomparable. As music affects a person in every way, the melody and its musical expression have a deep impact on a person's emotions, evoke different feelings and create different moods. The text and ideological content of the song affects not only the emotions, but also the minds of the listeners, excites them and makes them think. It creates a certain attitude in people towards the spiritual problems reflected in the work. Such influence is very complex and powerful.

In conclusion, it is worth saying that, taking into account the fact that music is a powerful educational tool, it is necessary to pay more attention to music classes in preschool educational organizations and ensure the regularity of these classes.

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